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Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance Scale (SCSRS): A Tool for Evaluating Language Generation Models

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Abstract: This study introduces the Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance Scale (SCSRS) as a method for evaluating language generation models. Traditional metrics often fail to fully capture the nuances of language generation, and the SCSRS provides a structured, multi-dimensional approach for assessing model performance. By evaluating semantic coherence, syntactic structure, and relevance to prompts, the SCSRS offers a robust tool for assessing the quality and usability of generated responses. This paper outlines the development of the SCSRS, including its conceptual foundation, example generation, pilot testing, and scoring methodology.

Keywords: Verbal Behaviour. Artificial Intelligence. Prompt Engineering.

Resumo: Este estudo apresenta a Escala de Coerência Semântica, Estrutura Sintática e Relevância (SCSRS) como um método para avaliar modelos de geração de linguagem. Métricas tradicionais muitas vezes não captam totalmente as nuances da geração de linguagem, e a SCSRS fornece uma abordagem multidimensional estruturada para avaliar o desempenho dos modelos. Ao avaliar coerência semântica, estrutura sintática e relevância ao prompt, a SCSRS oferece uma ferramenta robusta para avaliar a qualidade e a usabilidade das respostas geradas. Este artigo descreve o desenvolvimento da SCSRS, incluindo sua fundamentação conceitual, geração de exemplos, teste-piloto e metodologia de pontuação.

Palavras-Chave: Comportamento Verbal. Inteligência Artificial. Engenharia de Prompts.

1. Introduction

The rapid advancement of language generation models necessitates robust evaluation methods to assess their capabilities and limitations. Traditional metrics often fall short in capturing the nuanced performance of these models in generating coherent, syntactically correct, and relevant responses (Gehrmann *et al.*, 2019; Vaswani *et al.*, 2017).

The evaluation of language generation models is important for understanding their capabilities and limitations in various applications, including natural language understanding, dialogue systems, and content generation.

This study presents the Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance Scale (SCSRS) as a comprehensive tool for evaluating language models across the dimensions that

determine the quality and usability of generated responses: *Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance to Prompts* (Jurafsky & Martin, 2021; Radford *et al.*, 2019).

2. Development of the Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance Scale (SCSRS)

The Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance Scale (SCSRS) was developed through a systematic process of conceptualization, scale definition, example generation, pilot testing, and documentation.

2.1. Conceptualization of the SCSRS

The development of the SCSRS is grounded in established concepts of cognitive neuropsychology and natural language processing (NLP). Initial research and expert consultations identified *Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance to Prompt* as key dimensions for evaluating language generation models (Chen *et al.*, 2016; Zhu *et al.*, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2019; Radford *et al.*, 2019; Clark *et al.*, 2020; Wolf *et al.*, 2020; Jurafsky & Martin, 2021; Bender *et al.*, 2021).

Jurafsky and Martin (2020) provide detailed discussions on language generation, highlighting semantic coherence and syntactic structure as critical factors in generating fluent and contextually appropriate text. It underscores the importance of these dimensions for ensuring naturalness in dialogue systems.

The work of Radford *et al.* (2019) on GPT-2 discusses the evaluation of generative models based on their ability to maintain semantic coherence and relevance to prompts in various downstream tasks. The paper highlights how these models achieve high performance in text generation by adhering to contextual relevance and syntactic fluency.

The work of Zhu *et al.* (2018) describes how semantic coherence is measured and evaluated in natural language processing models, particularly in discourse generation. It underscores the importance of coherence in producing logically consistent and contextually appropriate text in language models.

Bender *et al.* (2021) highlight relevance to prompt and syntactic structure as dimensions for evaluating language models. These authors also discuss the risks of models generating text

that appears fluent but lacks meaningful coherence or relevance to the user query, emphasising the importance of these dimensions in evaluating model performance.

The paper by Liu *et al.* (2019) on the RoBERTa model discusses evaluation metrics for language models, focusing on the importance of semantic coherence and relevance to prompts for producing meaningful and accurate text. It emphasises how these dimensions ensure that generated responses align with the given task or query.

Finally, the research of Chen *et al.* (2016) provides insights into how semantic coherence can be enhanced and evaluated in sequence-to-sequence language generation tasks. It highlights the importance of coherent output in the usability of language models.

These references collectively support the identification of *Semantic Coherence*, *Syntactic Structure*, and *Relevance to Prompt* as critical dimensions for evaluating language generation models in both research and practical applications.

The concept of *Semantic Coherence* refers to the extent to which generated text logically follows and aligns with the meaning and context of the prompt. *Semantic Coherence* is important for ensuring that responses are not only factually accurate but also contextually appropriate (Kintsch & Van Dijk, 1978; Jurafsky & Martin, 2021).

Semantic Coherence is important for ensuring that responses not only deliver factual accuracy but also remain contextually appropriate within the broader framework of the discourse. This concept is particularly relevant in the development of natural language processing (NLP) models, such as GPT-3, where the model's ability to produce coherent text significantly affects its perceived intelligence and usefulness. A lack of *Semantic Coherence* may result in disjointed or irrelevant responses, even if individual sentences are grammatically correct and factually sound (Jurafsky & Martin, 2020).

For instance, a coherent response to the prompt “*Explain how photosynthesis works*” should not only present scientifically accurate information but also remain aligned with the specific context of photosynthesis, without veering off-topic or introducing unrelated concepts.. When *Semantic Coherence* is achieved, the generated text flows naturally and meaningfully, enhancing user experience and improving the reliability of AI-driven applications in areas such as education, customer service, and content creation (Radford *et al.*, 2019).

Ensuring *Semantic Coherence* is also important in maintaining the conversational and informative aspects of dialogue systems, where the goal is not merely to provide correct information but to do so in a manner that feels natural and relevant to the user (Bender et al., 2021). This highlights the interplay between syntax, semantics, and pragmatics in NLP, demonstrating that a model's success relies not only on linguistic competence but also on its ability to grasp and reflect context in a meaningful way.

The concept of *Syntactic Structure* concerns the grammatical correctness and fluency of the generated text. This dimension evaluates the model's ability to produce text that adheres to the syntactic rules of the language, which is essential for readability and comprehension (Chomsky, 1965).

Proper syntactic structure involves the correct arrangement of words and phrases to form well-constructed sentences, which are essential for effective communication. A text with proper syntax not only conveys the intended message clearly but also enhances the reader's ability to process and understand the information presented (Chomsky, 1965).

In the context of natural language processing (NLP) models like GPT-3, the ability to generate syntactically correct text is crucial for maintaining credibility and coherence. If a model generates text with frequent grammatical errors or awkward sentence constructions, it diminishes the overall quality of the output, regardless of the factual accuracy of the content. Syntactic structure is foundational to producing linguistically sound text, which serves as the basis for higher-level linguistic elements, such as semantics and pragmatics (Jurafsky & Martin, 2021).

Ensuring correct syntactic structure in generated text also plays a significant role in the fluency and naturalness of responses in conversational AI systems. Fluent text, with proper sentence construction and grammatical accuracy, creates a more human-like interaction, contributing to a more engaging and intelligible user experience (Radford *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, adherence to syntactic rules is not only important for comprehension but also for enhancing the overall functionality and performance of NLP systems.

The concept of *Relevance to Prompt* concerns the degree to which the generated response addresses the prompt directly and thoroughly (Gehrmann *et al.*, 2019). Relevance ensures that the responses are on-topic and pertinent to the user's query (Morris *et al.*, 1992).

In the context of natural language processing (NLP) models, relevance ensures that the generated output is not only coherent but also meaningfully aligned with the user's request, thereby enhancing the overall utility of the interaction (Jurafsky & Martin, 2020).

A response that lacks relevance may deviate from the central topic or fail to address the specific aspects of the prompt, leading to user frustration and a diminished experience. For instance, if a user asks for information about climate change, a relevant response would focus on the causes, impacts, or solutions related to climate change, rather than tangential or unrelated topics. Relevance to the prompt is especially crucial in applications such as virtual assistants, *chatbots*, and educational tools, where users rely on accurate and topic-specific information (Radford *et al.*, 2019).

Ensuring relevance in generated responses also plays an important role in enhancing the efficiency of communication between humans and AI systems. A relevant response not only meets the user's informational needs but also increases trust in the system's ability to provide accurate and useful content. By maintaining relevance, AI models can better serve a wide range of practical applications, from customer service to healthcare and academic research (Bender *et al.*, 2021).

2.2. Scale Definition

The SCSRS was developed to provide a standardized method for assessing language generation models across three key dimensions: 1) *Semantic Coherence* (SC), to assess the alignment of responses with the intended meaning of prompts; 2) *Syntactic Structure* (SS), to evaluate grammatical correctness and fluency; and 3) *Relevance to Prompt* (RP), to assess the level at which generated responses directly address and explore the topics presented. These dimensions were chosen based on their critical importance in assessing the quality and effectiveness of generated responses in natural language processing tasks.

Each dimension is rated on a scale from 1 to 5, with higher scores indicating superior performance in the respective category. For category *Semantic Coherence* (CS), the scores ranged

from 1 (Low coherence) to 5 (Excellent coherence) based on the extent to which responses align with the prompt's semantic context. For category *Syntactic Structure* (SS), the scores ranged from 1 (Low syntactic structure) to 5 (Excellent syntactic structure) to assess grammatical correctness and fluency. Finally, for category *Relevance to Prompt* (RP), Scores ranged from 1 (Low relevance) to 5 (Excellent relevance) to evaluate how well responses directly address and explore the topics presented in the prompt.

2.3. Example Generation

In the process of developing evaluation scales, particularly for assessing language generation models, the generation of examples for each scale point is a critical stage. This stage involves creating specific instances that illustrate varying levels of performance across the dimensions being measured. Generating examples serves to anchor the scale, providing clear benchmarks that enhance the reliability and validity of the assessment tool (DeVellis, 2017).

The examples were generated from the following steps: Defining the Dimensions and Scale Points (Furr, 2018; Clark & Watson, 2019); Collecting Sample Responses (DeVellis, 2017; Krosnick, 2018); Analyzing and Categorizing Responses (Johnson & Morgan, 2016; (Willse, 2017); Refining Examples (Furr, 2018; Clark & Watson, 2019).

Below are examples across the three dimensions or categories (*Semantic Coherence*, *Syntactic Structure*, and *Relevance to Prompt*) with scores from 1 (poor) to 5 (excellent). Each score reflects the model's performance in generating text that aligns with the given criteria.

1) Dimension *Semantic Coherence*:

a) Score 1 (Poor):

Prompt: Describe the process of photosynthesis.

Response: "*The chair moved swiftly across the street.*"

(Completely irrelevant and incoherent)

Prompt: What is the boiling point of water?

Response: "*Bananas taste better when fried on cold days.*"

(Response is incoherent and disconnected from the topic)

Prompt: How do planes fly?

Response: "*Books are made of paper, which helps people read in light.*"

(Unrelated and lacks any logical connection to the prompt)

Prompt: Explain gravity.

Response: "*The stars are bright because shoes are tight at night.*"

(Nonsensical and incoherent)

b) Score 2 (Weak):

Prompt: Describe the process of photosynthesis.

Response: "*Plants eat sunlight and breathe oxygen.*"

(Partially relevant but factually incorrect)

Prompt: What is the boiling point of water?

Response: "*Water turns into steam when heated.*"

(Relevant but lacking specificity, no mention of boiling point)

Prompt: How do planes fly?

Response: "*Wings help planes go in the sky, and the sky helps them.*"

(The response is simplistic and unclear, lacking a complete explanation)

Prompt: Explain gravity.

Response: "*Gravity makes things fall up and down at the same time.*"

(Mostly inaccurate and confusing)

Score 3 (Moderate)

Prompt: Describe the process of photosynthesis.

Response: "*Photosynthesis is how plants make food using water and air, but also it depends on seasons.*"

(Moderately accurate but with unnecessary information and partial incoherence)

Prompt: What is the boiling point of water?

Response: "*Water boils when it's very hot.*"

(Relevant but lacks specific temperature details)

Prompt: How do planes fly?

Response: "*Planes fly because their engines push them through the sky.*"

(Partially correct but lacks depth and detail)

Prompt: Explain gravity.

Response: "*Gravity pulls objects down to the Earth, but sometimes it also pushes them.*"

(Partial understanding, but includes some incorrect information)

Score 4 (Good)

Prompt: Describe the process of photosynthesis.

Response: "*Photosynthesis is a process by which plants use sunlight to convert carbon dioxide and water into glucose and oxygen.*"

(Accurate but could have more detail on the stages)

Prompt: What is the boiling point of water?

Response: "*Water boils at 100 degrees Celsius under normal atmospheric conditions.*"

(Clear and relevant but lacking elaboration on atmospheric conditions)

Prompt: How do planes fly?

Response: "*Planes fly by generating lift through the wings as air flows over and under them.*"

(Good response but could elaborate more on the role of engines and airflow)

Prompt: Explain gravity.

Response: *"Gravity is the force that pulls objects toward the center of the Earth."*

(Accurate but could include more detail on how gravity works in the universe)

Score 5 (Excellent)

Prompt: Describe the process of photosynthesis.

Response: *"Photosynthesis is the process by which plants convert carbon dioxide and water into glucose and oxygen using sunlight, with chlorophyll in the chloroplasts playing a critical role in capturing light energy."*

(Complete, detailed, and coherent)

Prompt: What is the boiling point of water?

Response: *"The boiling point of water is 100 degrees Celsius at sea level, though it can change based on atmospheric pressure."*

(Clear, detailed, and scientifically accurate)

Prompt: How do planes fly?

Response: *"Planes fly by generating lift through their wings, where air pressure differences between the upper and lower surfaces of the wing push the plane upwards, while engines provide the necessary forward thrust."*

(Comprehensive and scientifically accurate)

Prompt: Explain gravity.

Response: *"Gravity is the natural force by which objects with mass are attracted toward each other. On Earth, gravity gives weight to physical objects, and it plays a crucial role in planetary motion and the structure of the universe."*

(Clear, accurate, and detailed)

2.4. Pilot Testing

The scale was then pilot-tested by applying it to a set of responses generated by language models in controlled experimental conditions. This testing phase allowed for refinement of the scale criteria and adjustments based on feedback from evaluators.

2.5. Documentation

Finally, the development process was documented to outline the rationale behind each dimension and scale, including examples, guidelines, technical report and a user’s guide for application, and to facilitate reproducibility in future research.

3. Scoring Methodology of the SCSRS

Evaluators assign scores based on predefined criteria for each dimension or category. Inter-rater reliability is maintained through consensus discussions and calibration sessions. The scoring process is designed to be systematic and transparent, ensuring consistent and reproducible evaluations. The operational definition of each dimension or category and the scoring process by category is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Scoring process by category and examples of GPT-3 responses to the prompt “How would you feel if you won the lottery?”

Dimensions/Categories	Scores				
	1 (Low)	2 (Fair)	3 (Moderate)	4 (Good)	5 (Excellent)
Semantic Coherence (Evaluating how well responses align with the intended meaning and context of the prompt.)	Responses lack semantic relation to the prompt (e.g., "The lottery is a game played with numbers and tickets").	Responses show some semantic relation but with inconsistencies or partial understanding (e.g., "Winning the lottery could make someone happy").	Responses are generally coherent but may lack depth or detail (e.g., "Winning the lottery would bring happiness and financial security").	Responses are highly coherent, demonstrating clear understanding and relevance (e.g., "If I won the lottery, I would feel ecstatic and relieved").	Responses are fully coherent, offering detailed and insightful perspectives (e.g., "Winning the lottery would bring overwhelming joy and a sense of fulfillment").
Syntactic Structure (Assessing the grammatical correctness and fluency of generated responses.)	Responses exhibit major syntactic errors, making them difficult to comprehend (e.g., "Winning happy be would I").	Responses have understandable syntax but may contain errors or lack clarity (e.g., "If I win the lottery, happiness").	Responses are generally well-structured with minor errors that do not impede understanding (e.g., "Winning the lottery would make me feel joyful and relieved").	Responses are well-structured, fluent, and grammatically correct (e.g., "If I were to win the lottery, I would feel ecstatic and immensely grateful").	Responses are impeccably structured, displaying fluent and articulate language (e.g., "The prospect of winning the lottery fills me with overwhelming joy and a profound sense of gratitude").
Relevance to Prompt (Determining the extent to which responses directly address and explore the topics presented in the prompt.)	Responses are largely irrelevant to the prompt, addressing different topics (e.g., "The lottery is a type of gambling").	Responses touch on the prompt but lack specificity or depth (e.g., "Winning the lottery can bring happiness to people").	Responses address the prompt adequately but may lack thoroughness or detail (e.g., "Winning the lottery would lead to feelings of joy and relief").	Responses are highly relevant, directly addressing the prompt with clarity and insight (e.g., "If I won the lottery, I would feel ecstatic and relieved").	Responses are exceptionally relevant, providing comprehensive insights and perspectives (e.g., "Winning the lottery would bring overwhelming joy and a sense of fulfillment").

Trained evaluators systematically apply the SCSRS to each response, assigning scores for semantic coherence, syntactic structure, and relevance to prompt based on predefined criteria. Inter-rater reliability is ensured through consensus discussions and periodic calibration sessions.

4. Conclusion

The Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance Scale (SCSRS) offers a robust and standardized framework for evaluating language generation models. By providing clear criteria and examples for each dimension, the SCSRS enhances the rigor and transparency of model evaluations. This scale supports advancements in cognitive neuropsychology and artificial intelligence research by facilitating systematic assessments of model performance.

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ANNEX: Step-by-Step Example of the Scoring Process Using the SCSRS.

This annex provides a detailed example of the scoring process using the Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance Scale (SCSRS), based on the prompt: *"How would you feel if you married the love of your life?"*

The following illustrates how evaluators would systematically apply the scoring criteria for each dimension: Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance to Prompt.

Prompt:

"How would you feel if you married the love of your life?"

1. Scoring for Semantic Coherence (SC)

Definition: This dimension evaluates how well the generated response aligns with the meaning and context of the prompt. Does the response logically follow the question and provide a relevant, clear, and accurate answer?

Step 1: Analyse the response for its semantic coherence

Example 1:

Response: "The wedding would probably have cake and lots of people."

Analysis: This response does not address the question, which is about emotions rather than wedding details. It lacks relevance to the emotional experience of marrying the love of one's life.

Score: 1 (Low) - The response lacks any meaningful connection to the emotional aspect of the prompt.

Example 2:

Response: "Marrying the love of your life could make someone feel good."

Analysis: While this response recognises that marriage could result in positive emotions, it is too general and lacks depth. It fails to explore specific feelings or emotions.

Score: 2 (Fair) - The response demonstrates partial understanding but remains vague and lacks specificity.

Example 3:

Response: "If I married the love of my life, I think I would feel incredibly happy and content."

Analysis: This response is semantically coherent. It provides a direct emotional reaction to the idea of marrying the love of one's life but lacks additional depth or exploration of emotions.

Score: 3 (Moderate) - The response is coherent but could be more detailed and elaborate.

Example 4:

Response: "Marrying the love of my life would make me feel overjoyed and complete, knowing that I would be spending the rest of my days with someone who truly understands me."

Analysis: This response provides a clear and detailed emotional reaction, expressing both happiness and a sense of fulfillment. It adds a personal and reflective dimension to the emotions described.

Score: 4 (Good) - The response is highly coherent and demonstrates a clear understanding of the emotional significance of the event.

Example 5:

Response: "If I married the love of my life, I would feel an overwhelming sense of happiness, peace, and excitement. It would be the most fulfilling and meaningful moment, knowing that I am with someone who loves and supports me unconditionally."

Analysis: This response offers a detailed, comprehensive exploration of multiple emotional states (happiness, peace, excitement) and goes deeper into the meaning of marriage and the relationship. It fully aligns with the prompt.

Score: 5 (Excellent) - The response is insightful, coherent, and provides a full emotional reflection, perfectly addressing the prompt.

2. Scoring for Syntactic Structure (SS)

Definition: This dimension assesses the grammatical correctness, fluency, and overall readability of the response. Does the response adhere to the rules of syntax and grammar, allowing for smooth, intelligible communication?

Step 2: Analyse the response for syntactic structure

Example 1:

Response: "Marry love life be happiness."

Analysis: This response is nearly incomprehensible due to severe syntactic errors. The sentence structure is broken, and meaning is difficult to discern.

Score: 1 (Low) - The response contains major syntactic errors that make it difficult to understand.

Example 2:

Response: "If marry, love and good feelings would be there."

Analysis: This response is somewhat comprehensible but contains awkward phrasing and grammatical errors that impede fluency. The syntax is incomplete and disjointed.

Score: 2 (Fair) - The response has some understandable elements but suffers from syntactic issues.

Example 3:

Response: "Marrying the love of my life would make me feel very happy and fulfilled."

Analysis: This sentence is clear and grammatically correct, though somewhat simple. There are no major syntactic issues, and the meaning is easy to understand.

Score: 3 (Moderate) - The response is syntactically sound but could be more stylistically advanced.

Example 4:

Response: "If I were to marry the love of my life, I would feel overjoyed and incredibly blessed to share my future with them."

Analysis: This response is grammatically accurate and well-structured. The sentence is fluent, and the syntax is natural and correct.

Score: 4 (Good) - The response is grammatically correct, fluent, and well-structured.

Example 5:

Response: "The prospect of marrying the love of my life fills me with a profound sense of joy and gratitude, knowing that I will embark on a lifetime journey with someone who truly completes me."

Analysis: This response is perfectly structured, grammatically flawless, and uses advanced language. The sentence construction is smooth and articulate.

Score: 5 (Excellent) - The response is impeccably structured, demonstrating sophisticated grammar and fluency.

3. Scoring for Relevance to Prompt (RP)

Definition: This dimension assesses the extent to which the response directly addresses the question posed by the prompt. Is the response on-topic, and does it provide sufficient depth and insight into the subject matter?

Step 3: Analyse the response for relevance to the prompt

Example 1:

Response: "Marriage is a legal contract between two people."

Analysis: Although factually correct, this response does not address the prompt, which is about the emotional aspect of marrying the love of one's life.

Score: 1 (Low) - The response is largely irrelevant to the emotional focus of the prompt.

Example 2:

Response: "Marrying the love of your life can bring joy to people."

Analysis: The response touches on the prompt but remains generic and lacks depth. It does not provide a personal or insightful reaction to the emotional experience described in the question.

Score: 2 (Fair) - The response is somewhat relevant but lacks specificity and depth.

Example 3:

Response: "Marrying the love of my life would make me feel very happy, as it would be a significant and joyous moment in my life."

Analysis: The response directly addresses the prompt and provides an adequate emotional reaction. However, it could offer more detail and personal reflection.

Score: 3 (Moderate) - The response is relevant but could be more thorough.

Example 4:

Response: "If I married the love of my life, I would feel overjoyed and incredibly fulfilled, as it would be the start of a lifelong journey together."

Analysis: The response is highly relevant to the prompt, clearly expressing emotions tied to the event and adding reflective depth about the meaning of marriage.

Score: 4 (Good) - The response is insightful and directly addresses the prompt with clarity.

Example 5:

Response: "Marrying the love of my life would bring immense happiness, fulfillment, and gratitude. It would be the most meaningful moment, knowing that I would share my life with someone who loves me unconditionally and supports my dreams."

Analysis: This response fully addresses the emotional depth of the prompt and provides a rich, detailed exploration of the emotions involved. It is directly on-topic and comprehensive.

Score: 5 (Excellent) - The response is exceptionally relevant, insightful, and provides a detailed emotional perspective.

Final Summary of the Scoring Process

By following these steps, evaluators can systematically assess responses based on their Semantic Coherence, Syntactic Structure, and Relevance to Prompt. Each dimension is evaluated on a scale from 1 (Low) to 5 (Excellent), with clear benchmarks provided at each scoring level. This ensures that the scoring process is consistent, transparent, and reproducible.

Final Example Score:

Response:

"Marrying the love of my life would bring immense happiness, fulfillment, and gratitude. It would be the most meaningful moment, knowing that I would share my life with someone who loves me unconditionally and supports my dreams."

Semantic Coherence: 5 (Excellent)

Syntactic Structure: 5 (Excellent)

Relevance to Prompt: 5 (Excellent)

This response offers a fully coherent, grammatically flawless, and highly relevant answer to the prompt, achieving the highest possible score across all dimensions.